

Communication on Website and Some Notes When Using

Ths. Le Thi Minh Huyen

Vietnam Women's Academy, Vietnam

ABSTRACT: With the development of mobile devices, the reception habits of the media public have changed. Media companies, individuals, businesses, etc. always promote communication activities on digital platforms, especially social networking platforms. However, an indispensable basic platform in the development of multimedia communication in the digital age is website communication. Although this communication method was first born since the appearance of the internet, today it is still considered a long-term communication path. Therefore, to communicate effectively on the website, communicators are required to grasp the advantages, limitations and notes when implementing communication using this method.

KEYWORDS: Communication, website, multimedia communication, internet, digital platform.

1. The birth of Website (Web) and basic concepts

Tim Berners-Lee, a British computer scientist, invented the World Wide Web (WWW) in 1989, while he was working at CERN. The web was initially conceived and developed to meet the need for automatic information sharing among scientists in universities and institutes around the world. The basic idea of the WWW was to merge the emerging technologies of computers, data networks and hypertext into a powerful and easy-to-use global information system.

In March 1989, Tim Berners-Lee wrote the first proposal for the World Wide Web and the second proposal in May 1990. With the support of Robert Cailliau - a Belgian systems engineer, this was formalized as a management proposal in November 1990. In 1991, the first website was launched. This is a simple website containing information about Tim Berners-Lee's World Wide Web project.

Nowadays, with the continuous development of web technology, with advances in responsive design (can automatically adjust and display well on many different screen sizes, providing the best user experience on all devices), the web has become an essential part of daily life, serving many communication purposes. In modern life, everyone, every household can access websites anywhere with just a mobile device with an Internet connection. Users use a web browser to access electronic information pages. Each website will have an identifying address on the global network or intranet.

Website is a tool for exchanging information between media agencies, business organizations, organizations, individuals with the public and the community. For example, a sales website is a tool for exchanging goods between sellers and buyers. There, sellers introduce products and services to customers and they can buy and sell without having to meet in person. Or websites of multimedia media agencies such as dantri.com, vietnamnet.vn, vnexpress.net, vtv.vn, ... are a tool to convey the latest news to the public. On this website, the public can choose and search for information on the topic they want without spending much time.

Communication on website is a form of information transmission to the public on the web interface and has all the basic characteristics of multimedia communication (multimedia elements: Text, images, video, sound, graphics, interactive programs).

Communication on website is the process of transmitting information based on the website platform with HTTP protocol. Information content is transmitted to the public through text, images, graphics, sound, video on computers and mobile devices.

Today, organizations, individuals, businesses, and media agencies still focus on developing, creating and distributing information on websites along with social networking platforms on mobile devices.

2. Advantages of communication on website

The public receives a huge information database: The development of technology has led to the emergence of a series of websites. These websites can be owned by individuals, organizations, social groups, press and media agencies, domestic and global enterprises. The public has the opportunity to receive information from the huge data source that the website brings and freely chooses and receives it in many different ways, such as listening, reading, watching, interacting...

Ability to update information quickly, upload to the page easily, receive immediate feedback. Previously, when printed newspapers wanted to convey information to the public, they had to wait until the time and date of publication. Radio and television had to wait until the broadcast time. However, with the method of using the online version on the website, organizations, individuals, businesses, and media agencies can update, edit, and provide information easily, quickly, and conveniently, and at the same time, they can receive feedback from the public directly via text messages, emails, comments, etc. without spending too much time.

The public can easily access and search for information: With just a website address and a click, the public can easily access information quickly. In addition, there are countless information search pages, such as <https://www.google.com/>, <https://vi.wikipedia.org/>, <https://coccoc.com/search>,... All of these search pages are like encyclopedias that help the public search for information easily. In addition, each independent website has its own search engine. From here, the public can search for information and articles on the page by typing keywords into the search box. In addition, they can also comment, exchange information, and express their opinions with the author or with the readers themselves.

3. Limitations of communication on website

Information on websites can be falsified, making it difficult for the public to distinguish between real and fake: Because the mechanism for monitoring and managing information on the internet is still not strict and has many loopholes, it has created opportunities for high-tech criminals to fake information pages with the aim of reducing the reputation of agencies, organizations, groups, and individuals. From there, it can cause economic damage, reduce the reputation of organizations and businesses, or can also affect the public's psychology.

According to statistics from the Department of Information Security, in just the first 3 weeks of April 2024, the canhbao.khonggiamang.vn system received nearly 630 user reports on online fraud cases. Through inspection and analysis, experts from the Department of Information Security found that there were many cases of fraud impersonating agencies, organizations, businesses, suppliers, and large services such as some ministries, social networks, banks, emails, public services, etc. The number of fraudulent and fake websites that this agency warned online users about in March 2024 was more than 100 websites.

Faced with real and fake information, the public becomes confused, disoriented and difficult to distinguish. However, to block fake websites, the Information Security Department has deployed a warning system to prevent fake websites in the coming time. Data provided to the system from people and the IT systems of banks will help to promptly predict and detect fraudulent websites. Thanks to that, the coordination of internet service providers (ISPs) and telecommunications enterprises to resolve the issue will be faster and more timely.

Risk of information security loss and cyber attacks: Although the website has great security features, there is still a risk of being attacked by high-tech users, causing the website to be paralyzed.

According to Clause 8, Article 2 of the 2018 Law on Cyber Security, a cyber attack is an act of using cyberspace, information technology or electronic means to sabotage or disrupt the operation of telecommunications networks, the Internet, computer networks, information systems, information processing and control systems, databases, and electronic means.

On June 12, 2021, a number of individuals created fake accounts to attack many platforms of the online newspaper vov.vn, the newspaper's social networking platform on Google, the fanpage received negative comments, spam threats, and on Google Maps, the VOV application was rated 1* (1 star),... The climax was the denial of service attack (DDOS) targeting the website vov.vn, causing this site to be paralyzed, the public could not access it or could access it but the content and images on the website were no longer intact. According to Lan Ha (2021): "The cause of the attack is believed to be related to two articles published in the VOV online newspaper on June 12, about the phenomenon of taking advantage of social networks to make deviant statements, attack and insult individuals and organizations, affecting social order. The Department of Information Security, Ministry of Information and Communications assessed that this was an attack that had a serious impact on the VOV online newspaper. This was an attack targeting a state press agency, showing signs of serious violations of the law".

Not only electronic newspapers are attacked, but government organizations, businesses, and financial and banking organizations are also at high risk of cyber attacks such as encrypting internal network data, crashing websites, or infecting business emails with malware...

The 4.0 industrial revolution has brought benefits to the community, but also poses increasingly sophisticated threats to cybersecurity. Vietnam, like other developed countries in the world, will be greatly affected and face complex changes in this issue.

According to new data from Kaspersky Security Network (KSN), Vietnam's cybersecurity situation has shown positive signs in the second quarter of 2024 compared to the same period last year. However, with the increasing complexity of cyber attacks, maintaining high vigilance and investing in security solutions remains a top priority. From April to June 2024, Kaspersky successfully blocked 4,830,621 threats via websites on the computers of KSN security network participants. The number of website threats has decreased significantly compared to 7,713,485 in the same period in 2023, contributing to improving Vietnam's ranking on the global cybersecurity map. However, statistics show that 1 in 5 Vietnamese people have faced cybersecurity incidents on websites.

Thus, it shows that the risk of risk, loss of security, and being attacked is very high in the network environment. Cyber attacks always create pressures that threaten the stability of the political economy, as well as national network security. Awareness of preventing cyber attacks needs to be formed in the thinking of every person participating in digital technology today.

Transmission speed depends on bandwidth: Bandwidth is the amount of data transferred from the server to the user, a unit of measurement of the maximum amount of data that can be transmitted in a certain unit of time, usually calculated in seconds (s). For example, 60Mb/s means that the server can transmit at 60 million bits per second. Free websites often have a very limited bandwidth limit, which may slow down the access speed of users when accessing the website. For websites with wider bandwidth, the speed is faster, the connection and system are better. Therefore, the process of receiving information from the public on the website depends on the speed of the bandwidth. With websites with low bandwidth, if the number of people accessing at the same time can lead to overload and the time for the public to access information will take longer. This makes them frustrated by the waiting and may turn to use other websites with faster news access speed.

4. Some notes for users when communicating on the website

The public needs to be clear-headed when choosing information sources during the reception process: The website provides the public with a huge information store containing information from multiple sources, where there are many sources of information that ensure accuracy, but there is also no shortage of websites containing information that is not objective, has not been censored or can be faked. Therefore, in order for the public to not fall into a "mess of authentic - fake", choosing reputable websites to update information is necessary. The public needs to equip themselves with the knowledge and skills to distinguish between official information sites and fake news sites. From there, choose and receive information from reputable websites, valuable and quality information.

Promoting and improving the quality of information content on websites to attract the public: Since 2011, Google has emphasized the quality of content on websites. Accordingly, websites need to focus on investing in information content to attract public access.

According to data from SimilarWeb and other traffic analysis platforms, Google has consistently topped the list of the most visited websites globally, with about 85-92 billion monthly visits in recent figures from 2023 and 2024. This makes Google the most dominant platform on the internet, mainly thanks to its search engine function.

Social organizations, media agencies, and businesses need to focus on improving information security systems, anti-poison systems, and website protection. To prevent websites from falling into a state of loss of control leading to paralysis during operation, social organizations, media agencies, and businesses that own websites must have a strategy to increase site security.

To increase website security, the following factors should be paid attention:

+ Increasing the strength of the administrator password. Accordingly, when hackers attack, the first thing they do is to steal access from the website administrator. From there, they take control. Therefore, access accounts, especially administrators, need strong passwords. Strong passwords should contain all elements including uppercase and lowercase letters, numbers, and special characters. This makes it difficult for hackers to trace the password. At the same time, it is advisable to enable 2-step authentication or limit the number of system logins. If the number of logins exceeds the allowed number, the system will automatically prohibit that IP address from accessing.

+ Changing the URL (address of a single resource on the Web) to log in to the management page.

+ Scanning for malware regularly: Websites also need to regularly scan for malware to detect and handle it.

+ Updating and monitoring the website regularly: This is the best way to prevent hacker intrusion. With website versions, the website will have old applications and plugins that are not compatible. This is a big vulnerability for bad elements to exploit. In addition, you can use a web firewall, backup bandwidth, HTTP settings and SSL certificates.

REFERENCES

1. Lan Ha. (2021). *VOV electronic newspaper was attacked by cyberattack*. Retrieved from: <https://vnexpress.net/bao-dien-tu-vov-bi-tan-cong-mang-4294152.html>
2. Law No.: 24/2018/QH14, *Law on Cybersecurity*, June 12, 2018
3. Nguyen Thi Truong Giang. (2017). *Journalism and multimedia communication*, Hanoi: National University Publishing House
4. Nguyen Thu Huong. (2016). *The era of new media*. Journal of Political Theory and Communication, October 2016
5. <https://www.similarweb.com/website/google.com/>
6. <https://www.visualcapitalist.com/top-50-most-visited-websites/>